
**EFFECTIVE INCLUSION PRACTICES OF INCLUSIVE
EDUCATION**

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Abstract:

Teaching with an inclusive approach is a technique that aims to satisfy the needs of all students regardless of their cultural or ethnic background. This dynamic climate requires educators to be conscious of their own inner and outer selves as well as their students. Inclusive learning provides all students with diverse learning and effective ways to achieving educational objectives in safe and welcoming environments. Learning in an inclusive classroom is possible for students of all skills and disabilities, regardless of their age or ability level. It is based on the notion that all children and families are worthy and deserve equal opportunities to succeed in school. Making your classroom more inclusive doesn't necessitate major modifications or course redesigns. We can create equitable and transformative learning opportunities for all of our students by choosing to educate inclusively between student and instructor. Inclusive education and classrooms are able to fulfill the needs of children with disabilities while also benefiting their regular education peers.

Keywords: Inclusion, Inclusive education, Teaching Strategies, Children with special needs, Disabilities

Introduction:

Students without impairments benefit from inclusive classrooms as well as evidenced by their improved academic performance. Educators who support inclusiveness are more likely to utilize instructional practices that accommodate all students' learning styles. Students who learn alongside a student with a disability also have less prejudiced

views and are more accepting of persons who are different from themselves. Public attitudes and intentions are not met by the exclusion of children with impairments from education (Essary & Szecsi, 2018; Korepanova, 2011). Inclusive classrooms help children develop academically, emotionally, and socially. Most teachers devote the first few weeks of school, especially, to creating a classroom

environment in which all children feel included. A safe environment for students from all backgrounds, including gender, race, ethnicity, and sexual orientation goes further than the first month of the school year. According to fresh estimates from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics (UIS) that 73 million children of primary school age were not in school in 2010, down from a high of more than 110 million out-of-school children in the mid-1990s. There are no special schools in rural areas for the vast majority of Indians. In other words, an estimated 8 million children in India (MHRD 2005 estimates) are not in school because of factors such as poverty, ethnicity, impairment, and race. A study by Waldron, Cole, and Majd (2004) and Freeman and Alkin (2000) found that allowing children with and without special needs to learn alongside one another led to greater learning outcomes for everyone.

Meaning of Inclusive Education:

The term “inclusion” in English means “inclusiveness”. Inclusive education is the process of developing general education, which entails accessibility of education for all types of needs, in terms of responding to the diverse requirements of these children by finding the most effective approach to educate them. India's educational system has a very short history of inclusiveness.

For many years, children with disabilities were either sent to their own schools or not educated at all. Inclusion has improved gradually over time. In the beginning, schools established special education units in which children had little or no contact with their generally performing peers. Today, we are required to educate students in the least restrictive setting, which means they should spend as much time as possible in ordinary education classes. Our pupils' sense of belonging and inclusion are greatly enhanced when we provide a structured school environment (Trujillo and Tanner, 2014; Tanner, 2012)

Schools have not all modified their policies to be more inclusive despite the fact that regulations have changed. As a society, we have access to a wealth of information to assist us better understand the unique needs of students with disabilities. The inclusion of students with special needs in the mainstream classroom is more important now than ever because of advances in technology and understanding. It benefits all students.

Strategies for creating environment for all in Educational Institutes:

Schools and classrooms must be inclusive for inclusion to work. Teachers who identify students, make meaningful connections to their lives, and address their specific needs inspire students to take

responsibility of their learning environments (Ambrose et. al, 2010).

1. **Build Relationships:** It's essential for teachers to develop personal relationships with their students. The best way to to welcome each student individually at the door, inquire about their hobbies, and shower them with sincere praise while they're still in the building.
2. **Educate Yourself:** It is important for you to learn about a student's specific difficulties before working with them. Then, you can teach your pupils. Education paves the way for comprehension and comprehension paves the way for empathy and brotherhood.
3. **Coordinate with school stakeholder.** Inclusive education is part of a larger effort to make society more just and less discriminating for all disadvantaged people. So all stakeholders must provide their unique talents. NGOs can conduct creative but limited initiatives for certain groups. Their experiences must be assessed and shared to affect national implementation. Disabled persons in society require a continuum of services that includes medical, health, social, and community services.
4. **Implementation of general education best practices:** Curriculum and

instruction that emphasizes active student-centered learning, peer support, cooperative learning, critical problem-solving methodologies. These especially refer to classroom approaches that help students succeed by presenting and manipulating information and lessons in a variety of ways that provide the optimum opportunity for personal growth and development for each learner. Due to its inclusion as a model for inclusive education, this best practice lends credibility to the idea that effective educational institutions serve the educational needs of all students not only those with special learning requirements. All children's needs must be taken into consideration while developing curricula and teaching methods, as well as assessment criteria.

5. **Participation of children with disability.** Inclusion means providing education for all pupils equally in mainstream schools with individualised learning. Even though children with disabilities are in special classrooms, they should be able to participate in general education classes alongside their peers.
6. **Inclusive teacher training.** Teachers and other support staff who work with special populations in schools must receive high-quality training and

professional development. Teachers should be required to take at least one course on special needs students as part of their professional development. A solid understanding of children's unique learning styles and demands, as well as hands-on teaching experience, are essential for all teachers. Children with various learning needs and skills who would benefit from a more varied approach to education are present in every classroom, whether or not their teachers are aware of this fact. Of course, teachers who specialise in working with children with special needs will require additional training. In-service training is required to keep classroom teachers abreast of new advancements in inclusive education and to help them improve their general teaching skills.

Teaching Strategies for Inclusive Education:

Students from a variety of backgrounds can benefit from these teaching methods in the normal education setting. Principal and Teacher of the Institution is the centre point around whom everything revolves around. Role of proper leadership is very important. Every respect of inclusion-enrolment, retention, identification, assessment curricular and co curricular activities, learner friendly

evaluation, infact everything depends on the expertise and initiatives of the headmaster. Certainly for successful inclusion only headmaster and teacher is responsible. Willmore (2002) argued that teachers play a major role in the successful implementation of an inclusive education.

1. **Differentiate Instruction:** Differentiating learning opportunities allows all students to take part and learn at their existing abilities.
2. **Make Objectives Clear:** It is easier for all students to attain the goal of each session when the lesson's objectives are posted and reviewed in language that is age-appropriate. In particular, it is beneficial for disabled children.
3. **Adapt:** Teachers can adjust well. We continuously analyse our students, moving slowly when they don't understand and speeding up when they do. Those who are prepared for more are challenged and those who need it are supported.
4. **Activities:** Demonstrate for students and gradually hand over authority. Children with special need benefit greatly from the "I do, We do, You do" approach because it provides them with the help they

need to keep up with regular classroom activities.

5. **Positive Attitude:** As the instructor, your positive attitude toward inclusion creates a positive atmosphere for the entire class to follow.
6. **Teach to Different Learning Styles:** The best way to teach your children is to use a wide range of ways. Use a variety of teaching methods to ensure that all students are able to learn. If you were teaching writing and drawing lesson, you might include movement and rhythm into that lesson.
7. **Invite Guest Speakers to Share Their Stories:** The more pupils can identify with the racial or ethnic background of a teacher or guest speaker, the better their grades and the more engaged they will be with the material they are presented with. Allowing your pupils to interact with a guest speaker provides them with a unique learning opportunity.
8. **Manage Classroom Behaviors:** Teacher must priorities good classroom management in an inclusive setting as much as they do in any other setting. Educators need to develop

clear rules with goals and expectations, and they need to guarantee that students of all abilities understand and respect those standards in order for inclusion to succeed. A few examples of inclusive classroom management strategies:

- Putting up daily plans.
- Students should be made aware of the rules and expectations of the classroom.
- Providing opportunities for students to learn from each other.
- Assigning a certain time and place for each task might help keep everyone on the same path.
- Offering folders, labels and containers to help pupils better organise their materials.
- While pupils are working, you should be checking in on them.
- Use proactive rather than reactive measures as necessary.
- Disclosing any issues with students in a confidential setting.
- Specific, focused positive reinforcement should be given to students who accomplish behavioural or academic objectives.

Benefits of Inclusive Education for ALL Students:

General education instructors and special education teachers collaborate to address the needs of every student in general education for all. If the classroom has a diverse student population, it is possible for all of the students to benefit from the additional resources and supportive teaching methods. The goal of inclusive education is to develop new methods of teaching and other activities aimed at ensuring that all children have equal access to the classroom. Inclusion has a good side, and some of the benefits are as follows:

1. **Motivate the students:** Children with impairments or special needs can learn from their peers if they are included into a normal school. Children's abilities improve when they are together because they can motivate each other to perform better.
2. **Development of Communication skills:** Children with special needs benefit from increased interactions with typically developing peers because they learn to imitate their peers' way of speaking. During these conversations, other social skills such as a positive self-image are also transmitted.
3. **Life for Future:** To educate students with special needs for life outside of the classroom, inclusion is critical to the success they have outside of the classroom. Because of this, they will have a better chance of surviving in the future.
4. **Higher behavioral expectations:** When students with special needs are integrated into regular classes, they benefit from richer learning opportunities. Higher demands are placed on both students and teachers in terms of behaviour and academic performance. The talents that are learnt are refined and prove to be useful in the future.
5. **Parents Participation:** If you have a child with special needs, you may rest assured they will be accepted and have a chance to form true connections at school. A normal school life is made possible by the inclusion of children like these, who feel like a part of their schools' communities.
6. **Peer supporting:** The inclusion of non-disabled pupils has a positive impact on their academic and social development. When adolescents have peers with special needs, they gain a better understanding and appreciation for persons with a variety of

requirements. In this way, they are better prepared to live in a society that is more inclusive. The relationships that are built are significant because the majority of them assist their peers in becoming better.

7. Effective teaching skills:

Inclusion classroom teachers work with students from a wide range of backgrounds and abilities. Teachers can enhance or even develop new teaching abilities and distinguish activities for groups and those that involve all of the students when they have students of varying levels in their classrooms.

8. Development of Cooperation

feeling: Inclusion classrooms help students develop cooperation skills as they work together to devise the best academic plan possible to meet the requirements of students with special needs. There will be an exchange of ideas between educators, parents, and experts in the field.

Conclusion:

All pupils benefit from inclusion. All children benefit from the tactics teachers use to accommodate students with special needs in the normal education

classroom. Students' tolerance and empathy grow when students from all backgrounds and abilities are included in classroom activities. Inclusion is valuable. One of the most important components of inclusive education is that all children can engage in every aspect of the classroom. Educators, parents, and community leaders must work together to create better and more inclusive schools in order to tackle the difficulties. The Indian government is working to enhance its education system by focusing on an inclusive approach. It is imperative that we create an inclusive design of learning to ensure that all children are able to participate in the educational process in a way that is inviting, learner-friendly, and helpful to them. As a result, inclusion emerged as a viable answer to the problem of how to more successfully educate these youngsters. This strategy has a promising future. Inclusive education and classrooms can not only meet the standards of LRE for students with disabilities, but they also help regular education students. Both parents and instructors become more optimistic as a result of being exposed to the content. Regular education teachers can easily and successfully implement inclusive education with the help of training and assistance. Both parents and instructors become more positive as a result of exposure. Regular education

teachers can easily and successfully implement inclusive education with the help of training and assistance.

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